

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME:** Tizhe**FIRST NAME:** Emmanuel**PROGRAM CODE:** DMCR**COURSE CODE:** ACA-401D**PERIOD NUMBER:** 1**INSTRUCTOR:** Dr. Gulma**Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software: MSWord 365

ACHIEVING SUCCESS IN ACADEMIC WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

The primary purpose of a student-teacher relationship or encounter in a class is for learning to take place. This is because, in such a process of learning, knowledge is been transmitted from teacher to student, and sometimes from student to teacher as well. Euclid University is an institution that intends to bring out the best in her students. Thus, starting this program with course ACA-401D, which teaches the basics of international academic writing, aims at giving us a good foundation as it prepares us for all the other courses that will follow. In every structure that we have, we often notice that the bedrock on which the building stands determines the quality of the entire body of the structure. This defines why the builder goes into accurate measurements, and the use of good materials to obtain the quality desired of the structure. As a doctoral student in DMCR who will be writing a dissertation at the end of the entire program, I feel that the ACA-401D course is focused on molding me for that goal. That is why Euclid has given us the basic tools in this coursepack, and video records to guide us in our learning process. The exciting part about my starting this course is the fact that it will give me the opportunity to refresh my memory on the use of punctuations and writing styles. This will as well indicate some differences in words and spellings of US and UK use of English. But more importantly, to be conversant with how to organize my research work, main papers, and response papers through the use of proper punctuations, citations and referencing. The use of the video materials was the core guide in my orientation which gave me courage at the beginning of this course as I look forwards to seeing more videos as part of the teaching guide.

2) DETERMINATION TO ACHIEVE A GOAL

Some few years after I graduated from secondary school, one of my friends who was never interested in in-class assignments ended up as a journalist. This came as a surprise to me and all who knew him back in school. It was due to the inconsistency in having English teachers that made some of us not to be able to learn the basics of writing as of that time. Later I came to understand that, after leaving secondary school, my friend became determined to be a journalist, and he left no stone unturned in order to achieve his goal. That was why he studied journalism at the university.

In chapter one of our coursepack, the basics of writing are spelled out as the steps to perfecting our academic writings. This has to do with planning and thinking about what one wants to write about, which is the thesis question of the paper. It is this question that becomes the gadfly that directs the focus of one's discussion, analysis, and the use of supporting evidence from other texts (EUCLID 2019, 1–2). The ability of a person to organize his or her thought pattern forms the structure of the writing. This usually starts with the introduction of the paper to its conclusion (EUCLID 2019, 3). A very important aspect of academic writing is to share the views of other writers. It is either you agree with their views or not, provided you have your reasons to back up your argument. But you must acknowledge those authors whose work you have cited. This is where proper citing (in-text or footnotes) is very vital. The citing could be in long quotations, short quotations, or paraphrasing the idea into your own words (EUCLID 2019, 7–8).

I am quite certain that it was the desire to achieve his goals in life that made my friend to be determined to study journalism in the university which has now brought him into the writing world. Even though I learned most of the basics in my early school days and have encountered them in many different write-ups, yet I do not want to claim to be perfect in their usage in my written works. The starting of this program with course ACA-401D by EUCLID is indeed a welcome idea for me. Here I would want to note that the act of plagiarism draws my attention to the necessity of acknowledging the person whose research work I have cited in my paper. Not doing so is unfair to the author and deserves some penalty (EUCLID 2019, 5).

3) PUTTING OUR KNOWLEDGE INTO PRACTICE

The ability of a writer to make the proper use of the style guide in his or her work indicates the extent to which such a person has understood the rules and is consistent in its usage (EUCLID 2019, 24). This is because different rules are recognized in writing by different institutions. For example, when I did my master's program in Negotiation, Conflict Resolution and Peacebuilding (NCRP), the California State University Dominguez Hills emphasized the use of APA as its rules of writing. Here in this program, Euclid recommends the Chicago Rules (Turabian), and also, the use of American English (Ibid.). Even though the UK and US versions of English are both recognized universally, but the choice of which one to use is a matter of institutional principle. So, it is expected

that, when one uses the writing styles especially in the different spellings of words and punctuations, we must be careful not to confuse the two. For example, the UK and US spellings of these words are slightly different. Axe-ax; plough-plow; colour-color; centre-center; cheque-check (EUCLID 2019, 27-28). These differences were difficult for me to understand when I first came to the United States and was doing my master's program. Some of the challenges I struggled with included the use of different concepts, terms or expressions. For example, hire a car, Petrol, Boot, Barrister. All these are UK use of English, while, rent a car, Gasoline, Trunk, Solicitor are American use of English words (EUCLID 2019, 30). It was a gradual process for me to come to terms with the use of these expressions.

There are several other differences between the UK and the US English that we may come across. We need to be careful when using them in our writings. In a very unique way, my attention was drawn to the use of periods, commas and quotation marks. These may look insignificant sometimes, but their right placements bring out the proper meaning of words used in a context. Even though I am familiar with the use of comma (,), period (.), and quotation marks (“ ”), yet what is new to me is where to place the period after closing a quotation as used either in the US or in the UK English. For the US use, the period or comma comes before the closing quotation mark, while in the UK use it comes after the closing quotation mark (EUCLID 2019, 35). So, having a good knowledge of these differences in styles of writing and using them correctly will help in writing good academic work.

4) THE PROPER USE OF WORDS

Putting my thoughts together and logically analyzing them help me in coordinating my plans for academic writing. I have attended paper presentations in which one can see and know how the writer carefully selected his use of words. Sometimes it is not easy to make such choices especially when you need to distinguish between academic work and a regular use of language. Chapter seven of our coursepack is a good sample paper that has pointed out some of the words that are not often proper for use in academic writings which we need to avoid. This reminded me of when my homiletics teacher in the seminary once said to us in class, that if we are giving a homily, it should be a homily. If it is a reflection, it should be a reflection. This made me to be confused because I felt that the two are the same. I later realized that these have a thin line separating them.

From the sample correction papers, I have come to understand that, there are conventional words that can be used to flow with one's thoughts in writing. For example, one should use the word 'Threatening' or 'unsettling' instead of using the word 'serious.' Also, one can use 'intervention' instead of 'interference' (EUCLID 2019, 36). It is also understandable here that, the repetitive use of a conjunction in the same sentence makes it sound monotonous. That is why alternative words like 'and,' 'or,' 'also,' can be used for the flow of ideas in a writing (EUCLID 2019, 36). Other times, it is important to break longer sentences into shorter ones to avoid too much use of conjunctions in the same sentence (EUCLID 2019, 39). In this case, I'm guilty of such mistakes sometimes. Whenever I try to express my ideas about an issue, I often end up with long sentences

than I intend to write. Knowing the tools of good academic writing and the proper use of words at a particular time gives great quality to a write up. The many samples and examples that are found in the last two chapters of our coursepack with several definitions and abbreviations, were helpful in clarifying terms and words which I did not know in the past (EUCLID 2019, 44).

5) VISUAL ASSISTANCE

In the introduction of this paper, I mentioned that learning is the passage of knowledge from one point to another. From the one who knows to the one who does not know. But the ability to acquire knowledge differs in different individuals. In a school setting for example, students learn either by listening to the teacher or by watching the visual aids used by the teacher to communicate the knowledge. I remember when I was studying for my Post Graduate Diploma in Education (PGDE) some years back, one of the courses taught was 'Micro Teaching in Class.' This simply taught how to use teaching aids in class to convey the intended message to the student.

The uses of video clips are some of the most effective visual aids through which learning can effectively be communicated. In the orientation for this program and in the reading materials, the video records that were used connected with me because I'm a visual learner. It was through the orientation video in this course that I first heard about 'Zotero' which completely put me off at first because, it was something that had to do with the computer, and I'm not an expert in it. Watching the video, again and again, helped me to know and see how it works. That took away some pains from me. Similarly, the video for the study materials guided me on the use of the styles guide. It helped me to know how to format my template, use of headers, quotes and the rules of punctuations. Through the video instructions, most of the information in the CMS Crib Sheet was made practical and understandable as they deal with rules and styles of writing a good academic paper (Ibid.). I am glad to have had the opportunity to learn new things through the use of the visual aids which gave me more confidence than when I first started the course.

6) CONCLUSION

I have not been a great writer of long essays, but my desire to learn and do more keep pushing me to do my best. This course on how to write International Academic Papers is appropriate for the start of this program. To some extent, it has brought back memories of what I learned in the past and has many more to offer which are new to me. EUCLID has introduced me to the 'Turabian' style of citing and referencing which is different from the 'APA' that I used during my master's studies. This is exciting for me because it has given me the opportunity of acquiring new knowledge which is what learning is all about. ACA-401D has helped me to know the use of Zotero which is a completely new experience for me. Very often I have cited my work or referenced them manually, but this makes it easier and faster. Even though it was a challenge for me to

figure out how to use it, but it was worth going through the process. The use of the 'Template' is another new experience for me as it is my first time to use it. It made my work to be neat, well arranged, and scholarly. Another benefit achieved in this course is how it has pointed out the differences between the UK and US use of English which were often confusing to me. The most interesting thing here is the fact that, even where to place the punctuations are different from each other in some cases. These differences are also seen in some of the spellings of words. With the tools and styles of writing that this course has introduced me to, I believe it is a sure way to achieving the goal of my studies.

REFERENCES

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